

Chromatographic Studies on Metal Complexes. Part III. Paper Chromatography of Square Planar bis (1-amidino- O-alkylurea) Complexes of Copper(II) and Nickel(II)

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Manuscript received 19 July 1974; accepted 11 April 1975

A paper chromatographic study of a series of square planar bis(1-amidino-O-alkylurea) copper(II)/nickel(II) complexes in aqueous KCl-pyridine developers has been made. R_f values decrease in the order: Ni(II) > Cu(II). Solubilities of the complexes in developers are believed to play a more significant role than the inductive effects of the substituent groups and hydrogen bond forming abilities of the ligand. An equilibrium of the following type

can neither be proved nor dispelled.

BIGUANIDES (BigH; I) and 1-amidino-O-alkylureas (AAUH; II) are closely related ligands^{1,2}.

Both the series of ligands provide similar square planar bis(ligand) metal(II) complexes. A paper chromatographic study of bis(1-amidino-O-alkylurea) complexes of copper(II) and nickel(II) in aqueous KCl-pyridine developers is reported in this communication.

[Biguanide, R = H; Alkyl-substituted biguanide, R = alkyl group.]

Methods and Materials

The complexes were obtained by following published procedures^{3,4}. Their purity was checked by elemental analysis and spectral measurement. For the purpose of putting spots copper(II) and nickel(II) complexes of AMUH, AEUH, APⁿUH, APⁱUH (M = methyl; E = ethyl; Pⁿ = n-propyl; Pⁱ = isopropyl for R in structure (II)) were dissolved in warm water. The remaining complexes of ABⁿUH, ABⁱUH, AAⁿUH and AAⁱUH (Bⁿ = n-butyl; Bⁱ = isobutyl; Aⁿ = n-amyl; Aⁱ = isoamyl) were dissolved in ethanol. The following developers were examined:

Developer I : Distilled water (~100 ml)
 " II : 100 ml 1(M) KCl
 " III : 100 ml 0.5(M)KCl+5 ml Pyridine
 " IV : 100 ml 1(M)KCl+5 ml Pyridine
 " V : 70 ml 0.5(M)KCl+30 ml (1:1) Pyridine.

Ascending paper chromatography was adopted⁵. For the detection of copper(II) and nickel(II) complexes rubenic acid in ethanol was found satisfactory. R_f values (Figs. 2 and 3) were reproducible to within $\pm 0.02 R_f$ units. Solubilities (Figs. 1, 2 and 3) were determined by shaking at room temperature (29°-30°) a known excess of the complex salt in a suitable volume of the developer (10, 20 or 25 ml) for 3 hr. The excess was filtered off, washed with a few drops of ice cold water, dried and weighed.

Results and Discussion

We have checked spectrophotometrically that none of the complexes undergoes any drastic change in any of the developers so that they are chromatographed as genuine complexes.

In distilled water (Developer I), the complexes either did not travel at all or diffused to a long distance along the filter paper. Cationic complexes are known to be strongly held on the negatively charged cellulose anion of the filter paper^{5,6,7}. Such strong attraction could be reduced by using developer II. But this developer II was also regarded unsuitable as the spots were too large (16-18 cm). Developer III provided satisfactory spots (~3 cm) for bis(1-amidino-O-alkylurea) complexes of copper (II) only. Unfortunately, this developer provided big sized spots (~7 cm) for bis(1-amidino-O-alkylurea) complexes of nickel(II). Suitable sized spots (2.5-3 cm) of both bis(1-amidino-O-alkylurea) copper (II) and nickel(II) complexes are obtained by using developer IV. With this developer although increasing the chain length of the alkyl substituent led to an increase in the R_f values for copper(II) complexes

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(from methyl upto isopropyl derivatives), no such increase in R_f values was marked for the corresponding nickel(II) complexes.

Effect of alkyl substitution :

In our previous studies⁵ with bis(substituted biguanide) metal(II) complexes we have shown that on increasing the chain length of the alkyl substituent on the N^1 -atom of biguanide (I) the R_f values of the corresponding copper(II), nickel(II) and palladium(II) complexes also increase substantially. The two factors, [1] hydrogen bond formation between the cellulose anion and the N^1 -atom of biguanide and [2] the inductive effect of the alkyl group were considered responsible for increasing the R_f values. Our previous qualitative conjecture⁵ that on increasing the chain length of the alkyl substituent solubilities of bis(substituted biguanide) metal(II) complexes decrease in aqueous KCl-pyridine developer has now been confirmed on a quantitative basis (Fig. 1).

Thus solubility could not be held responsible for the increasing R_f values with increasing chain length of the substituent in the cases of biguanide complexes.

In the present case of the 1-amidino-O-alkylureas, the hydrogen bond formation remains invariant throughout the series because alkyl substitution does not lead to any decrease of hydrogen atoms in the ligand backbone. As against this, alkyl substitution of the N^1 -atom of biguanide does lead to a decrease of the available hydrogen atoms. But the inductive effect of the alkyl group remains. We believe that solubility factor plays here a greater role since the solubility of the copper(II) complexes in aqueous KCl-pyridine (developer IV) is found to increase with increasing chain length of the alkyl substituent (from methyl upto isopropyl derivatives, Fig. 2).

The increase in R_f values of the copper(II) complexes is thus in conformity with the increasing solubility of the complexes to a certain point (isopropyl derivative),

Fig. 1. Variation in solubilities and R_f values of bis(biguanide/substituted biguanide) copper(II) chlorides in developer IV with substitution. A₁, solubility curve; A₂, R_f curve.

Fig. 2. Variation in solubilities and R_f values of bis(1-amidino-O-alkylurea) copper (II) and nickel(II) chlorides in developer IV with substitution. A₁, solubility curve of copper(II); A₂, R_f curve of copper(II). B₁, solubility curve of nickel(II); B₂, R_f curve of nickel(II).

and thereafter solubilities and R_f values decrease and attain a somewhat steady level.

The solubilities of the nickel(II) complexes pass through two maxima and from isopropyl derivative onwards follow the trend of the corresponding copper (II) complexes although these solubility changes can not influence the R_f values any more because the R_f values have already attained a comparatively high level in the starting compound $[\text{Ni}(\text{AMUH})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ (R_f 0.85, Fig. 2). It is our conviction that changes in solubilities of a family of closely related complexes can influence the R_f values only when they do not start with an already high value. That this suggestion is not entirely unfounded is revealed on an inspection of the R_f values and the solubilities of the complexes in developer V. In this developer, the solubility differences are enormous, (compared to

We have reported earlier⁵ that with higher concentration of pyridine and lower concentration of KCl (developer V) the homochelate $[\text{Cu}(\text{BigH})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ provided two spots which was traced to be due to an equilibrium of the type :

In view of the above results it appeared likely that 1-amidino-O-alkylurea complexes of copper(II) would also provide two spots of substantially different R_f values. We have, however, obtained a single spot which was somewhat bigger in size than shown by $[\text{Cu}(\text{Py})_4]\text{Cl}_2$. In view of the fact that $[\text{Cu}(\text{AMUH})_2]\text{Cl}_2$, $[\text{Cu}(\text{AEUH})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ etc. and $[\text{Cu}(\text{Py})_4]\text{Cl}_2$ exhibit spots with about the same R_f values in this developer

Fig. 3. Variation in solubility and R_f values of bis(1-amidino-O-alkylurea) copper(II) chlorides in developer V with substitution. A_1 , solubility curve; A_2 , R_f curve.

those in developer IV) but the changes in R_f (Fig. 3) are minimal. Note that the starting compound $[\text{Cu}(\text{AMUH})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ has a R_f 0.84 in developer V while its R_f in developer IV is only 0.68. The levelling effect of the R_f values of nickel(II) complexes in developer V is still more apparent since the R_f of starting compound $[\text{Ni}(\text{AMUH})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ is 0.90 instead of 0.85 in developer IV.

Effect of size of the Complexes :

R_f values increase in the order : $\text{Ni} > \text{Cu}$, in the order of decreasing size and weight : $\text{Ni} < \text{Cu}$ (Fig. 2).

Effect of KCl/pyridine :

Like bis(biguanide) and bis(substituted biguanide) complexes of copper(II) and nickel(II), R_f values of bis(1-amidino-O-alkylurea) complexes of copper(II) and nickel(II) also increase on increasing the KCl concentration in aqueous KCl-pyridine developer. It is to be noted that neither KCl nor pyridine alone can give good spots. With lower concentration of KCl and higher concentration of pyridine (developer V) all the complexes provided good spots (~ 1 cm) and higher R_f values compared to those with developer IV. This is also due to increased solubility of the complexes in this developer (Figs. 2 and 3).

it is not unlikely that the two expected spots have got fused together. Equilibrium of type (1), therefore, has neither been definitely established nor dispelled in the case of bis(1-amidino-O-alkylurea) copper(II) complexes.

Acknowledgement

This is a pleasure to acknowledge our indebtedness to the CSIR for financial assistance to one of us (R.K.R.).

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